

Residual Paramagnetism of Cobalt in Carbonato-Ammine and Oxalato-Ammine Cobalt (III) Complexes

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Magnetic susceptibilities of carbonato-ammine and oxalato-ammine cobalt (III) complexes measured by Gouy method indicate a substantial contribution of the second order paramagnetic of cobalt atoms. The observed values for the residual paramagnetism are found to be always larger than those calculated on the basis of the ligand field theory of Griffith and Orgel¹².

It is well known that trivalent cobalt forms a number of spin-paired diamagnetic octahedral complexes. The earlier work^{1'2'3} reported that the observed diamagnetic susceptibilities of cobalt (III) complexes are much smaller than those of computed from the susceptibilities of constituent atoms and established that these complexes display a certain amount of residual paramagnetism of cobalt.

Our interest in the magnetic properties of these series of complexes arose from the theoretical work of Griffith and Orgel⁴ who calculated, on the basis of ligand field theory, the amount of second order paramagnetism in octahedral spin-paired complexes of Co^{3+} and Fe^{2+} in which the transition metal has d^6 configuration. The theoretical work of Griffith and Orgel⁴ has however, found support in the nuclear magnetic resonance of ^{59}Co in some cobalt (III) ammine complexes. The experimental data on chemical shifts of ^{59}Co observed by few workers⁵, on cobalt (III) complexes indicated that the shifts are predominantly due to second order paramagnetic term arising from the mixing of $^1A_{1g}$ and $^1T_{1g}$ states.

As the Griffith and Orgel's theory⁴ satisfactorily explains the n.m.r. data of very few complexes, a careful study of magnetic susceptibilities of carbonato-ammine and oxalato-ammine cobalt (III) complexes has been undertaken for careful examination of the theory.

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EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of complexes and their analytical data are given elsewhere⁶. The magnetic susceptibility of the complexes under study were determined in solid state by Gouy method at room temperature. The electronic spectra were recorded by "Hilger uvispeck" spectro-photometer, using 1 cm matched quartz cells.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The susceptibility data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The diamagnetic corrections $\Sigma\chi_D$ for constituent atoms were calculated assuming Pascal's additivity rule for all compounds. The data used for diamagnetic correction (in units of 10^{-6}) are^{7,8}: $\text{Co}^{3+} = -10$; $\text{Cl}^- = -23.0$; $\text{CO}_3^{2-} = -34.8$; $\text{NO}_3^- = -20.0$; $\text{H}_2\text{O} = -13.3$; $\text{NO}_2^- = -13.1$; $\text{K}^+ = -17.5$; $\text{NH}_3 = -17.1$; and $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-} = -34.0$.

The results indicate that the observed (χ_m) values for all the complexes are much smaller than $\Sigma\chi_D$ values. The difference between the two is obviously due to residual paramagnetism (χ_p) due to cobalt.

The values of χ_p observed for carbonato or oxalato ammine cobalt (III) complexes increase in the order: hexammine < pentammine < tetrammine < triammine < diammine < (monoammine) < tris carbonato or tris oxalato (without ammonia ligand).

From the above order it can be concluded that the successive replacement of ammonia ligand by CO_3^{2-} or $\text{C}_2\text{O}_4^{2-}$ ligand in these complexes of cobalt (III) results in increase in χ_p values. These results are in line with previous work of Rosenbohm¹ and Belova and Syrkin². From the theory of Griffith and Orgel, it is obvious that the ligand field strength should decrease in the same order. To compare this order with spectrochemical series, absorption spectra were studied. The $d-d$ band energy separation between ground and next excited state of cobalt has also been calculated (Table 1). The order obtained from both the spectral and magnetic data is similar except mixed ligand complexes containing nitro ligands which may play an important role in increasing or decreasing the order of ligand field strengths.

From the Griffith and Orgel's; theory⁴, χ_p values have been calculated (Table 1).

The mixed ligand ammine complexes and tris carbonato or oxalato-ammine complexes show rather good agreement but other ammine complexes have low χ_p values. A lack of good agreement between the observed and calculated χ_p values may partly be due to the uncertainties in the values of diamagnetic susceptibilities used for the evaluating of $\Sigma\chi_D$ term and also partly due to the bonding effects. One way to allow for any departure from pure d orbitals is to introduce an orbital reduction factor k , which will have a net effect on the magnetic susceptibility when the matrix elements of spin moment are small compared to orbital moment. According to Griffith⁹ for pure d orbitals $k = 1$ and for low spin complexes of first transition series k will be close to unity and $(1-k)$ being the measure of the

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TABLE 1

Magnetic susceptibility Data for (a) carbonato-ammine cobalt (III) and (b) oxalato-ammine cobalt (III) complexes

Complex	$\chi_M \times 10^6$	Energy separation for ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{1g}$ from $d-d$ band cm^{-1}	$\Sigma\chi_D \times 10^6$	χ_p (obs) $\times 10^6$	χ_p (calc) $\times 10^6$	k (orbital reduction factor)
a) 1. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{CO}_3]\text{NO}_3 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$	-35.79	20410	156.1	120.3	200.2	0.80
2. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{CO}_3]\text{NO}_3 \cdot 0.5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ cis.	-12.90	19080	139.0	126.1	214.1	0.77
3. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{CO}_3\text{Cl}] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	+12.72	18150	131.6	144.3	225.1	0.80
4. $\text{K}[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{CO}_3)_2] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	+24.24	17270	143.0	167.3	236.6	0.84
5. $\text{K}_2[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)\text{CO}_3(\text{NO}_2)_3] \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$	+40.92	21740	148.7	189.6	181.9	1.02
6. $\text{K}_3[\text{Co}(\text{CO}_3)_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	+52.84	15870	204.4	257.2	257.3	1.00
b) 1. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_5\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]\text{NO}_3$	-36.72	19800	149.5	112.8	206.3	0.77
2. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_4\text{C}_2\text{O}_4]\text{NO}_3$ cis.	-16.65	19530	132.4	115.4	209.1	0.74
3. $[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_3\text{C}_2\text{O}_4\text{Cl}]$	+5.154	18690	118.3	123.5	218.6	0.75
4. $\text{K}[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)_2(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_2]$	+31.98	17950	129.7	161.7	227.6	0.84
5. $\text{K}_2[\text{Co}(\text{NH}_3)\text{C}_2\text{O}_4(\text{NO}_2)_3]$	+93.37	21830	135.4	228.8	187.1	1.10
6. $\text{K}_3[\text{Co}(\text{C}_2\text{O}_4)_3] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$	+574.00	16560	204.4	778.4	256.7	—

THE VARIATION OF χ_p obs WITH MAX FOR a) CARBONATO AMMINE COBALT (III) AND b) OXALATO AMMINE COBALT (III) COMPLEXES

deviation of actual orbitals from being pure orbitals. Values of k have been calculated for all these complexes under investigation from root of the ratio of χ_ρ (obs) to χ_ρ (calc) and are given in Table 1. It is observed that these values vary between 0.7 and 1.1. The results show a trend similar to that observed by Asmussen and Ballhausen¹⁰.

The theory⁴ expects a linear relation between the χ_ρ (obs) and λ_{\max} . The validity of this relation was tested by plotting the graph of χ_ρ (obs) values against λ_{\max} for these complexes (Figs. 1 and 2). We found that the plot was approximately a straight line although mixed ligand complexes behave differently. The χ_ρ (obs) value of tris complexes is being much higher than the χ_ρ (calc) value (not shown in case of tris oxalate complex). This may be due to the paramagnetic nature of the complex¹¹.

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